

HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE ART OF PAINTING AND LEADING PAINTERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation

This article provides detailed information on the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people, the main part of our cultural heritage of folk arts and crafts, material evidence in the primitive community system, and the leading role of decorative and applied arts in the Iron Age.

Keywords: Paleolithic period, Painting, Schools of Painting.

In the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people, folk decorative arts have been a key part of our cultural heritage. Originating and flourishing in the Uzbek land, the applied arts are world-renowned for their uniqueness and uniqueness. When we think about this stage of development, we see that the origin of Uzbek applied decorative art dates back to the earliest period of mankind, that is, the period of primitive society.

Archaeological excavations in our country have shown that the creation of artifacts by the human body began in the Stone Age and has been going on for centuries.

We have the material evidence of the primitive community system - tools of labor and hunting, furniture and ornaments, the remains of human settlements. Underground historical monuments, human and animal remains, paintings and reliefs on snow and basement walls are important sources for studying the history of primitive society.

During the Paleolithic period, examples of applied and decorative arts began to spread. Archaeologists are still struggling to gather enough evidence before reaching the final conclusions about the origin of the artifacts. As people became more sedentary, observing the laws of nature led to an increase in their sense of symmetry, rhythm, and form. He created a unique art of painting, which is based on the smooth repetition or interweaving of the same elements. Painting became widespread in the New Stone Age (Neolithic), influenced and contributed to the development of decorative and applied arts. Decorating pottery and other items with patterns became widespread. Parallel, spiral and wavy lines, circles form the basis of many patterns of this period. Geometric patterns were gradually enriched with schematic drawings from the worlds of humans, animals, and

plants, and expanded in content. Its elements continued to reflect the symbolic signs of the cosmic forces. For example, a socket is a symbol of the sun, a wavy line is a symbol of movement, a symbol of water, and so on.

The art of painting has now not only served a decorative function, but has also begun to express the Rocky and philosophical concepts of the people.

During the Bronze Age, pottery flourished in Central Asia. The advent of pottery made the artwork more elegant and beautiful. The red background found in Chust is notable for its ceramics with black paintings and patterns.

Decorative and applied arts also play a leading role in the Iron Age. In addition to geometric patterns, the use of plot compositions in decoration is especially developed.

Various decorative arts and crafts, weapons of war, hunting and labor found in the underground and tombs also play an important role in the study of the art and culture of ancient Central Asia. The ceramics are made of bronze, gold, and silver, and the surface of the items used for human needs is decorated with patterns, embossed images, and sculptures. The surface of some objects reflects life events. These factual materials serve to understand the art and culture of the past, the aesthetic and artistic views of the people.

It is known from archeological excavations in Uzbekistan that the art of painting has developed in Khorezm, Sogd, Bactria and other regions. Remains of paintings and patterns found in the excavations of Buddhist temples Fayoztepa (I-II centuries), Dalvarzintepa (I-century) in Surkhandarya region are a clear proof of this.

The "Amudarya Rich" (Ox Rich), discovered by the upper reaches of the Amu Darya, plays an important role in understanding the artistic life and culture of Central Asia in the IV-VI centuries BC. Among the monuments now housed in the British Museum in London are gold statues, various jugs, bracelets, rings, seals, coins, gold chariots and weapons.

Alexander the Great (Alexander the Great) defeated the Achaemenid Empire in the 4th century BC and conquered much of Central Asia. Only the nomadic tribes of Khorezm, Fergana and Syrdarya retained their independence.

As a result of such a deep philosophical approach to applied art, the creation of works of art based on conditionality, stylization and symbolism has intensified. This historical factor has given impetus to the rapid development of the Uzbek national decorative art, and today our world-famous architectural monuments testify to the wonderful harmony and integration of pottery, tile, painting, calligraphy, stone carving and other arts. Folk applied decorative art enriches the spiritual world of people, forms their artistic taste and nurtures

their psyche. That is why the Uzbek folk art is one of the most important sources in the artistic, moral, universal education of people, in the formation of their scientific outlook, as well as in raising their cultural level.

In the recent past, the most developed types of Uzbek applied decorative art, such as painting, pottery, stone and bone carving, carving, knitting, embroidery, jewelry, embroidery, gold embroidery, carpet weaving, felt, basket weaving unique performance technologies, real national names, their specific terms, schools, styles specific to these arts, and the services of renowned masters in these fields are known all over the world.

The art of painting in Central Asia has long been known around the world. The magnificent buildings built by our ancestors in the past have not lost their charm to this day. The tastefully crafted patterns still amaze us today. A pattern is an Arabic image that means a flower, and it is an ornament created by repeating in a certain order the shapes of birds, animals, flora, geometry, and so on.

As a result of following the requirements of Islam, the depiction of animals, birds and people disappeared and painting developed. The Arabic script has been mastered. The result is an epigraphic style with patterns. The Arabic inscription was drawn along with the patterns. The Arabic script served as both an ornament and a prayer spell.

Painting as an art form has long been an important part of Uzbek culture. Over the centuries, his artistic traditions have emerged and developed. Unlike all other types of art, the patterns show the interdependence of generations, the continuity of national traditions. The tradition of painting as a method of studying this type of art has been passed down from grandfather to father and from father to son. Due to this continuation, the art of painting is still preserved. The best examples of the pattern are distinguished by the expediency and beauty of the forms combined through a rich creative imagination. This reflects the difference in the views of folk masters on the environment. The game of drawing in the pattern, like the melody in the music, the song and the fairy tale, may consist of "a great generalization of the life experience of the people."

Artistic painting is the art of creating beauty in a combination of colors and unique compositions. In his work, the artist skillfully uses the natural luster and harmony of colors, beautiful shapes, textures of materials to achieve a bright expression.

In the traditional architecture of Uzbekistan, painting is mainly used to decorate ceilings, silent vodka, palace pillars, mosques, schools, houses of the rich, wooden items. The rhythmic movement of intertwined twigs, horns and

luxuriously depicted flowers in delicate floral-geometric patterns, the Islamic motifs in the works of Uzbek masters and the classical motifs of girih patterns are adapted to the shape of the ceilings. The pattern serves to decorate more interiors and covered porches and porches.

Today, the pattern is used in architecture, home furnishings, gifts, small wooden toys, musical instruments, and household items.

The art of painting is gaining momentum today. Through the press, radio, television, and cinema, people become acquainted with these works of art and its folk masters. Among these artists are O. Kasimjanov, Ye. Raufov, A. Boltaev, S. Norkuziyev, A. Azimov, A. Isayev, B. Abdullayev, T. Tukhtahojayev, J. Khakimov, Z. Basitkhanov, M. Turaev, T. Akhmedov, K. Karimov, A. Ilkhomov and others. The works of our national masters and their students are exhibited in the Museum of Applied Arts in Tashkent, exhibition halls, art salons, as well as in residential and public buildings, such as the Tashkent State Circus, Alisher Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater, National Academic Theater. can be seen in administrative and residential buildings such as the Drama Theater, the Museum of the History of the Temurids, the buildings of the Oliy Majlis and the City Hall, metro stations, hotels. The task is to expand the network of clubs in schools and out-of-school institutions as much as possible. The study of folk art helps to develop students' artistic taste, diligence and a number of useful knowledge and skills. Helps to identify and develop their creative abilities.

Schools of painting. During the khanate, masters of folk arts began to gather in cities such as Khiva, Kokand, Bukhara, Samarkand. Painters from Fergana and Bukhara often came to Samarkand, and masters from Kokand and Margilan came to Tashkent to decorate many buildings. This will play an important role in the further development of painting schools, the creation of unique compositions, the further enrichment of the color scheme. But even though these patterns are similar, each school of painting differs with its own composition, style of work, color scheme.

Tashkent School of Painting. Tashkent patterns are distinguished by their elegance and gradual transition of colors, strict adherence to a certain color, the frequent use of geometric and floral patterns. Patterns are often done in green. Intricate girih patterns, which are clearly stylized with Islamic patterns, are also widely used.

Olimjon Kasimjanov, Yakubjon Raufov, Jalil Khakimov, Toir Tokhtakhojayev, Zokir Basitkhanov, Mahmud Turaev, Anvar Ilhamov, Komil Karimov and others are the founders of the Tashkent School of Painting.

Y. Raufov has created wonderful compositions, preserving the traditions of the Tajik school of painting. The artist skillfully uses the rich cultural heritage of Uzbek-Tajik patterns, creating many compositions of Islamic and geometric patterns. Its patterns are distinguished by the brightness of their colors and their harmony with each other. He discovered new elements in his compositions. Raufov exaggerated the patterns and used daily techniques. T. Tokhtakhojayev was able to create complex compositional patterns. The master's golden-brown pattern was a new step in the development of the Tashkent School of Painting.

Jalil Khakimov, a talented student of Olimjon Kasimjanov, who made an effective contribution to the development of the Uzbek school of painting, and a teacher of many students who created a unique school of painting, is a teacher. The master's services are great in restoring the patterns created by our ancestors from ancient times. If we pay attention to the patterns of J. Khakimov, the patterns in them are rich in elements, clear, smooth, bright green. He did a lot of flower arrangements. J. Khakimov is an artist who has thoroughly mastered the traditions of the Uzbek national art of painting and successfully continued it. Master-made tables, chairs, boxes and other items are highly valued in many countries around the world. His work developed in the spirit of Eastern traditions and left an indelible mark on history.

Khiva School of Painting. The Khiva pattern is radically different from the Samarkand, Tashkent, Fergana and Bukhara patterns. The Khiva pattern uses a lot of blue and green colors. The composition of the Islamic pattern consists of a twig, a marjoram, a flower, a leaf, a pea, a flower, and a simple aigul. Often star-shaped girdles are used, enriched with a spiral Islamic pattern between them. Khiva patterns are generally based on madoxilli patterns. The Islamic pattern is made in the form of a spiral capillary. Abdulla Boltaev, Ruzimat Masharipov, Odamboy Yakubov, Eshmurad Sapayev and others are the bright representatives of Khiva school of painting.

Bukhara and Samarkand schools of painting. Bukhara is characterized by the complexity and attractiveness of the composition. In the patterns of Bukhara, intricate knots are used in a precise and precise size, and the floral patterns pay special attention to the rhythm of leaves, fruits and flowers.

The patterns of Samarkand are similar to those of Tashkent and Fergana. Samarkand patterns are characterized by extreme flowering, extreme mobility of leaves and flowers. The patterns are done first in blue and then in green.

Masters such as master Rahmonqul, master Jamoliddin, master Abduzoxid, master Sharif, master Alimjon, master Boki, and later masters Jalal and Bolta

Jalilov laid the foundation of the Samarkand School of Painting and made a great contribution to its development.

It is very important to comprehensively study and analyze the history, values, masterpieces of science and culture of the peoples of Uzbekistan. "Today we have such a historic opportunity," said President Islam Karimov. we need to apply it to construction. " To this end, a number of documents of the government of the republic are aimed at the development of our country on the basis of comprehensive world standards. In particular, in educating young people, great importance is attached to the use of our culture, values, samples of national art, wonderful works of art created by our ancestors and famous all over the world.

Uzbek folk art is known all over the world for its antiquity, richness and diversity of culture. Every historical monument in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Termez, Tashkent, Fergana and other cities, every example of applied folk art is a unique, priceless work of art created by our ancestors and is one of the masterpieces of world culture. rin received.

Our cultural and spiritual wealth, accumulated over the centuries, in particular, the most developed types of Uzbek folk applied decorative arts: painting, pottery, wood carving, stone carving, bone carving, carving, knife-making, jewelry, embroidery, the real original names of the masters, their unique schools, the styles they created were in danger of gradually disappearing during the former Soviet regime.

Today in our independent republic there are ample opportunities to preserve, appreciate and use the applied decorative art created by our people as a result of centuries of creative work, to develop the aesthetic taste of young people and bring them up as highly cultured people. . World-renowned scholars, poets and artists such as Al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Al-Khwarizmi, Imam Bukhari, Bahauddin Naqshband, Ahmad Yassavi, Alisher Navoi, Kamoliddin Behzod, Zahiriddin Babur called for the pursuit of beauty. Our ancestor Amir Temur, with the help of craftsmen and scientists, paid great attention to the development of mathematics, geometry, architecture, astronomy, literature, linguistics, history, music, fine arts and calligraphy. It strives to make cities beautiful and glorious in every way.

In the IX-X centuries in Turan the art of painting developed rapidly. Bricklaying is highly developed in architecture. The use of plaster and wood carvings on the interiors of buildings is highly developed. In particular, the roofs of the tombs, walls and arches are very elegantly decorated with ganch patterns.

World-famous scientists, poets and painters such as Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Al-Khwarizmi, Nizami Ganjavi, Nasir

Hisrav, Kamoliddin Behzod, Maoniy, Firdavsi, Umar Khayyam, Babur captured the imagination of our buildings. attractive, inviting to decorate with beautiful patterns of nature. People are encouraged to be close friends and brothers with beauty.

Take, for example, the old city center of Samarkand, the Sherdor Madrasa in Registan. Its roofs, huge domes and beautiful towers, colorful mysterious tiles and elegant, luxurious, luxuriously decorated silent facade amaze. This madrasa, like other architectural monuments, has its own content and history.

During the reign of Muhammad Imamqulikhan, one of the Ashtarkhanids in Bukhara, the khan's most trusted and close confidant, Yalangtoshbiy Bahodir, the ruler of Samarkand, became very rich. This magnificent building will add splendor to the city and will be praised by all poets, scholars, scholars and people of the city. Yalangtoshbi Bahadir set the task of informing the architect Abdu Jabbor that he would not lag behind his great ancestors in anything. The famous architect, who held the key to art, was able to convey the philosophical idea in a silent voice to the people through the language of patterns. The main façade of the Sherdor Madrasa is attractive, its roof is symmetrically decorated with symbolic patterns, red-gold tiger lions are chased by delicate oxen, and the smiling man from their land is framed by the golden light. . They are surrounded by Islamic motifs.

In the image, the agile, strong, invincible lion is symbolically referred to as Yalangtosh Bahodir, and the ohu is depicted as a symbol of weakness. The sun was taken as a symbol of that time and life. Blue tiles reflect the universe and peace, and delicate floral patterns reflect the garden and nature.

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